

Determinant and Practice of Referral Services at Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Asaba, Delta State

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Abstract

Access to quality healthcare has been a perennial challenge for residents in many emerging cities in Nigeria. In Delta State, the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Asaba, is a tertiary hospital that plays a pivotal role in the city's healthcare referral system. Ideally, any patient should first seek care from the lower levels of the healthcare system before presenting at a tertiary facility. This study aimed to determine the institutional and individual factors that influence patient referrals to FMC, Asaba. The survey included 405 respondents, and proportionate sampling was used to establish the sample size. A cross-sectional and descriptive approach, employing qualitative and quantitative data collection methods, was used to explore patterns of patient self-referral. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was utilized for descriptive and inferential statistics, including Chi-square tests and Logistic Regression, with results considered significant at a p-value < 0.05. The study revealed that only 27.7% of patients seeking healthcare at the hospital opted for self-referral to FMC. A significant relationship between gender and the inclination to seek referral services was observed. Surgical complications (28.6%) emerged as the most common health problems among patients who self-referred to FMC. Institutional factors influencing patients' choice of FMC, Asaba, included the location and accessibility of the hospital, availability of medicines and equipment, quality of care, a clean and beautified environment, and the attitude of medical personnel. Health problems prompting patients to seek services at FMC, Asaba, often require high-level diagnostic healthcare, which may not be readily available at lower healthcare levels. The study underscores the need to strengthen and expand primary and secondary level hospitals to mitigate inappropriate use of tertiary referral hospitals, a trend contributing to congestion.

Keywords: *Referral System, Tertiary Hospitals, FMC Asaba, Self-referral, Institutional Referral, Referral factors*

Introduction and Statement of Problem

The effectiveness and efficiency of a nation's healthcare system hinge on the organization and structure of its medical services. Quality healthcare accessibility is pivotal for a country's socio-economic progress. Unfortunately, diverse obstacles, encompassing economic, physical, and social factors, hinder numerous individuals, particularly in Africa, from obtaining effective healthcare services, resulting in complications and fatalities (Oladipo, 2014; Titus, 2015).

In the medical domain, the referral concept is a common practice adopted by healthcare providers when facing limitations in addressing a patient's diagnostic and therapeutic requirements (Akande, 2004;

Abodunrin *et al.*, 2010). Referral systems, whether internal, external, or between public and private facilities, play a crucial role in ensuring continuity of care. Successful referral systems establish close ties between different healthcare system levels, guaranteeing that patients receive optimal care in proximity to their residences (Al-Mazrou, *et al.*, 1990).

Studies on the accessibility of referral hospital treatment in countries such as Nigeria and Ethiopia indicate a distance-related decline in service utilization, suggesting that individuals residing farther from referral centers are less likely to access clinical services (Kloos, 1990; Iyun, 1983). In Nigeria, the constitution mandates the provision of accessible healthcare services at

various government levels. However, challenges persist in delivering quality healthcare, with facilities predominantly concentrated in metropolitan areas and catering to higher-income groups (Westendorf & Ghai, 1995; Afolarami *et al.*, 2008).

The healthcare service gap between rural and urban areas has led to medical migration and health-seeking behaviors, facilitated by referral techniques. Referral techniques include formal referrals within the healthcare system and self-referral, where patients independently select healthcare facilities. While extensive research has been conducted on self-referral, formal referral, particularly in urban centers with competitive health clinics, has received limited attention (Preker & Carrin, 2004; Kiranandana & Apairatr, 1990).

Early referral is pivotal for optimizing healthcare and patient management (Wavamunno & Harris, 2005). However, a weak link in the referral system across different healthcare levels in Nigeria places a significant burden on secondary and tertiary care levels. This research aims to evaluate the utilization of available referral healthcare services in urban areas, using the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Asaba, as a case study. Achieving this entailed: creating a demographic profile of patients, analyzing the proportion of self-referral and institutional referral, scrutinizing factors influencing referral services, identifying the

types of illnesses, and the origin of referred patients. The objective is to understand the factors influencing and impeding the referral system in Nigeria and provide recommendations to ensure that individuals, regardless of their socio-economic status or health challenge, can access quality healthcare.

Materials and Methods

This section provides a concise overview of the research design, the research area, the study population, sample size determination, and the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Research Design

The research utilized a cross-sectional descriptive design and collected data through both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. Spatial analysis of referral services at the Federal Medical Centre in Asaba, Delta State, was the main focus of the study. Patients requesting medical attention at the Federal Medical Centre were the subjects of the data collection, which happened between July 1 and July 31, 2018.

Study Area

The research was conducted at the Federal Medical Center, Asaba, Delta State, situated along Nnebisi Road, Asaba. Refer to Figure 1 for the geographical representation of Asaba, highlighting the Federal Medical Center

Figure 1: Map of Asaba showing the Federal Medical Center, Asaba

Sampling Frame

The target population for this study comprised all patients seeking health services at FMC, Asaba. The sample size was determined based on the average number of patients seen in various departments, statistics obtained from the Records department. Approximately 1,200 patients were recorded in hospital wards and other areas, forming the study population. The researcher, due to limitations in the classification of records, employed a comfortable level of classification and selected willing participants for the study. In cases where referred patients were unable to communicate due to illness, their caregivers were interviewed. However, certain categories of patients were excluded from interviews or questionnaire administration, such as patients suffering from psychotic disorders, and those with insufficient medical information to suit the research purpose.

Sample Size

Simple random sampling was utilized to select 405 patients from various wards at FMC, Asaba. The selected wards included were female and male surgical wards, pediatric, children's emergency, neonatal, obstetrics and gynecology, orthopedic, eye clinic, maternity, and accident and emergency.

Data Collection Techniques

This study utilized data obtained from primary and secondary sources. Two primary methods were used in collecting primary data: observation and questionnaires administered by interviewers. Walks through the hospital wards were conducted to observe and assess congestion levels, the professionalism of hospital staff, and the cleanliness of selected wards. Secondary data were sourced from hospital records to obtain information on the average number of patients seen, prevalent health problems, and

the ratios of health workers (doctors, nurses) to patients.

Data Collection Techniques

Before commencing the study, ethical approval was obtained from the FMC Ethics Committee. Each member of the research team possessed a copy of the authorization letter from the Ethics Committee. Courtesy visits were made to the departmental heads, where the research assistants introduced themselves, presented the letter from the FMC Ethics Committee, and then proceeded to interview patients in waiting queues (for outpatients) or hospital wards (for inpatients). Thereafter, the research team moved to entry points (selected wards and outpatient clinics) and used the previously mentioned stratified random selection techniques to select the patients.

Structured questionnaires administered by the research assistants were employed to collect demographic information, reasons for hospital visits, patient waiting times, factors influencing health facility choice, and patient satisfaction with services at FMC. Data on hospital congestion levels and hospital staff's adherence to good client relations when treating patients were gathered through observation using a checklist. The GPS coordinates of all the hospitals from which patients were referred, as well as those of FMC Asaba, were collected with a handheld GPS.

Method of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for data analysis, using SPSS version 16.0. Descriptive statistics were employed to identify the most frequently reported health problems leading to self-referral across age groups. Using chi-square analysis, the significance of correlations between the several components (individual and institutional) under investigation and the probability of self-referral to FMC was

evaluated. A relationship is deemed statistically significant if the p-value is less than 0.05 (<0.05).

Table 1: Sampling Size Table

Ward and Unit Selected	No of Patients Selected.
General Outpatient Department (Neurology, diabetes, cardiothoracic, Urology, Rheumatology) and Emergency.	104
Eye Clinic	79
Obstetrics and Gynecology and Female Medical ward	65
Cardiology	12
Dental Unit and Male Medical Ward	85
Surgery and General Medicine	60
Total	405

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic status of the research sample

The socio-demographic profile of the research population is shown in Table 2. 195 (48.2%) of the 405 respondents were male, while 210 (51.8%) were female. The majority of participants (68.4%) were under 45 years old.

Origin of Referral for Referred Patients

Figure 2 shows the percentage distribution of both self-referred and institutionally referred patients at FMC Asaba. A majority (72.3%) of participants were referred from lower levels of healthcare, while 27.3% of patients went straight to FMC, Asaba, for medical care without a referral. Remarkably, most referrals lacked written documentation

Table 2: Socio-demographic status

Particulars	Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	195
	Female	210
Age	45 years and below	274
	Above 45 years	126

Source: Authors' fieldwork (2025)

Figure 2: Percentage Proportion of Referred and Self referred patients at FMC

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

Origin of referral for referred patients

Figure 3 illustrates the origins of referral for institutionally referred patients. Private hospitals accounted for 40.1%, government hospitals 24%, and traditional healers 0.7%. Specialist clinics and mission-based spiritual homes contributed 29% and 6.2% respectively. A significant portion (72.1%) of patients referred to FMC, Asaba, originated from the lower healthcare levels, such as primary healthcare centers and maternity

clinics. Overall, 57.4% of the institutionally referred cases were from other government health facilities, probably influenced by proximity and financial considerations. Essentially, Figure 3 depicts the adherence level to referral processes within the tiered healthcare system, highlighting that most patients seeking medical attention at FMC, Asaba were referred from the primary and secondary healthcare facilities.

Figure 3: Origin of referral for referred patients

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

Referral and Self-Referral Determination

Referral and self-referral were determined using the bypassing disclosed by respondents. Bypassing has an impact on the effectiveness of the healthcare system and the actual coverage of medical treatments. It is viewed as a powerful predictor of people's healthcare preferences (Leonard *et al.*, 2002). This study assessed bypassing using patient-reported information on their awareness of alternative healthcare providers in their area. (Akin & Hutchinson, 1999).

The GPS coordinates for the hospitals were imported as CSV and overlain as points over a base map of Delta State within ArcGIS Pro 3.03. This generated a visual display of the proximity and spread of the hospitals in relationship to FMC, Asaba. The farthest distance by crow flight is from Ugbolu Primary Health Center, at about 24.02km while the shortest distance by crow flight is from Life Value Hospital, opposite Stadium, Asaba, at about 0.56km. Figure 4 shows the OD Cost Matrix of the hospitals in relationship to the FMC, Asaba. It also shows the flow pattern of referral services from lower healthcare centers in Asaba metropolis. Figure 4: Map Showing Distance between Referral Hospitals to the FMC, Asaba. The flow chart reveals that most clients from primary healthcare centers move to FMC Asaba, the main tertiary health care center in the city. Many do not mind the far distance as they are assured of quality healthcare. Ogwash Uku General Hospital which is 21.8km away, Ugbolu Primary Healthcare centre at 24.3km and Government Hospital, Ibusa 11.3km are the farthest that patients travelled to seek medical care at FMC Asaba. Other healthcare centers are within reach at less than 5km.

Influence of Gender on Referral The association between gender and referral status at FMC is detailed in Table 3. According to the Odds Ratio, women are 1.4

times more likely than men to self-refer. This suggests that nearly equal proportions of male and female patients, are seen at the hospital among those institutionally referred and self-referred.

The data presents a notable gender disparity in the number of women and men referring or self-referring to FMC, Asaba, primarily due to challenges associated with women's health. It can be deduced that gender influences self-referral, aligning with findings from a comparable study on avoiding lower levels of healthcare in Tanzania (Leonard *et al.*, 2002). The Tanzanian study found that females commonly self-refer to tertiary healthcare due to the perceived quality of maternal care they received and newborn health services, especially during childbirth.

From Table 4, it is evident that surgical operations (24.9%) and pediatric-related issues (24.1%) are major reasons patients are referred, either institutionally or through self-referral. Other health problems include infectious diseases (17.0%) and non-infectious diseases (16.6% institutional, 28.6% self-referral). Cancer, cardiac, respiratory tract disorders, and eye complications are also prevalent health issues among patients seeking services at FMC, Asaba, with surgical complications being the most significant health problem among self-referred patients.

Institutional determinants of self-directed referral at FMC, Asaba

Patients listed the following four institutional factors as the main reasons for choosing FMC, Asaba, for their medical needs: the hospital's easily accessible location; its stellar reputation; quality healthcare service; welcoming staff; and immaculate surroundings and grounds. To confirm these responses, the researcher conducted several transect walks to assess the degree of

congestion in various randomly selected clinics and wards. The observation was that the majority of the wards were clean and well-kept. Patients who were critically ill and highly susceptible to infections were treated at the Accident/Emergency Department, contributing to the exceptional cleanliness of the premises. On the other hand, patient sharing of beds was a typical occurrence in several wards due to overcrowding.

Table 5 provides a statistical review of the institutional elements impacting self-referral

at FMC. Findings show statistically significant correlations between self-referral and specific institutional characteristics. These statistically significant factors include: Location of FMC (χ^2 :21.844, df:2, p value: 0.002), Availability of medicines at the hospital (χ^2 :17.003, df:2, p value:0.02), Clean surroundings (χ^2 :25.816, df:2, p value:0.001), and Admission procedures (χ^2 :19.947, df:2, p value:0.005). The findings were significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 3: The Relationship between Gender and Referral

Gender	Referred		Self-referred		Odds Ratio 96% CI	2 χ Test of significance
	No.	%	No.	%		
Male	148	50.7	47	42	1 (Reference)	$\chi^2=2.465$ d.f= 1 P Value= 0.122
Female	144	49.3	65	58	1.41	
Total	292	100	112	100		

Table 4: Health problem patient commonly referred at FMC, Asaba

Illness Types	Institutional Referral		Self-Referral	
Surgical Operation	57	24.9 %	43	24.1%
Pediatric Related illness	62	27.1%	42	23.6%
Gynecological and Maternal Health problems	33	14.4%	28	15.7%
Infectious diseases	39	17.0%	12	6.7%
Non-Infectious diseases.	38	16.6%	51	28.6%

Source: Authors' Computation

Table 5: Summary of institutional factors influencing patients' decision to seek health services directly at FMC, Asaba

Variables	Important (%)	n	Chi-Square value (d.f)	P value	Variables
Proximity	46 (11.4)		21.844 (2)	0.002*	Location
Affordability and accessibility of services	15 (39.1)		7.028 (2)	0.43	Affordability of services
Status of the hospital	13 (32.7)		8.414 (2)	0.29	Reputation of the hospital
Availability of medicine and equipment	15 (38.6)		17.003 (2)	0.02*	Availability of medicine
Quality of service care	9 (22.8)		11.713 (2)	0.11	Quality of care
Clean and beautified environment	20 (50.5)		25.816 (2)	0.001*	Clear kept surroundings
Admission procedure	17 (43.3)		19.947 (2)	0.005*	Admission procedure

*A few of the patients (who self-referred) stated that more than one factor was crucial.

Table 6: Table of Referral (Origin of referred Patients to FMC)

Types of Hospital (Classification of Hospital)	Location and Address
1. Tertiary Hospital	Federal Medical Center, Asaba
2. General Hospital	General Hospital, Okwe Ibusa General Hospital, Ibusa Road Ogwashi General Hospital, Ogwashi
3. Primary Health Care Centers	Oshimili South Health Care Center, Express Ugbolu Health Care Center, Ugbolu Okwe Health Care Center
4. Specialist Hospital	Iconic Clinic, Nnebisi Road Mmaduemezu specialist DBS Temple Clinic Anwai Road. St Rebecca, Mami Market
5. Standard Private Hospital	St Luke's Hospital, DBS Road Comfort Consult Hospital Lifeshield Hospital NNPC, Okpanam Life Value Hospital Opposite Stadium.

The hospital's easy accessibility and the affordable treatments it provides are two important considerations for patients seeking healthcare at FMC Asaba. Furthermore, those interviewed stated that they preferred the hospital's medical services because of the availability of state-of-the-art diagnostic technology, excellent staff character, high-quality service care, and cleanliness and attractiveness of the surroundings.

Table 6 presents the locations of the various hospitals where most referrals come from within Asaba town. The table provides the classification of the hospitals, categorizing them into: tertiary, general, primary healthcare centers, specialist, and standard private.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The effectiveness of the referral system in FMC, Asaba, depicts its role as one of the most operational healthcare facilities in the city. Health professionals are faced with a wide range of disorders, from basic illnesses to complicated, life-threatening problems that call for cooperation between several facilities at different hierarchical levels of care. The referral system's efficacy stems from elements such as the availability of skilled staff, well-equipped facilities, and logistical support for the referral process.

A strengthened healthcare system is crucial for providing access to healthcare services for a country's citizens. Appropriate referral systems are indicators of a robust health system.

To further enhance the functioning of referral systems in Asaba town, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Given the increasing population in Asaba, it is recommended to establish more tertiary-based referral centers to

handle a variety of diseases and illnesses.

- ii. Government intervention is necessary to extend the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) coverage to lower-income earners in urban areas, ensuring proper access to health services.
- iii. To address the inadequacy of doctors and nurses at FMC, Asaba, the government should prioritize employing more qualified personnel.
- iv. Efforts should be made to limit brain drain by providing conducive working conditions.

With the increasing rate at which medical personnel are leaving Nigeria, in the "Japa" phenomenon, there is an urgent need for a comprehensive overhaul of the country's healthcare system.

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